

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL NATURE OF LISTENING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8017344>

Ravshanova Nasiba Karamatovna

*A senior teacher of Foreign Language department
Karshi engineering-economics institute, Uzbekistan.*

Annotation.

This article focus on listening is a receptive type of speech activity, with an immediate impact from the listener's reaction. It can be direct, contact, or indirect, and is complex due to the irreversible nature of communication.

Key phrases.

listening, receptive type of speech, difficulties in listening, communication situation, Listening mechanisms;

Listening can act as an independent type of speech activity (for example, listening to reports, films) or enter into dialogic communication as a receptive component, being one of the sides of speaking. Listening, unlike speaking, is a receptive type of speech activity. The form of its flow is internal, unexpressed. However, the listener affects the communication: his reaction (laughter, remarks, and gestures) causes an immediate impact. Thus, listening is a reactive type of speech activity.

Listening can be direct, contact (dialogical communication) and indirect, distant (radio and television broadcasts). Listening is a complex type of speech activity, since the processes of listening in real communication are irreversible and cannot be analyzed and fixed. New information replaces the old, what has been said disappears irrevocably. Often there is not enough time to think about what was heard, and therefore understanding is often not achieved and the communication process is disrupted. Let's take a closer look at the auditing process from a psychological and physiological point of view.

As we have already said, listening refers to the receptive type of speech activity and is the perception and understanding of speech by ear at the time of its generation. The following components are necessary for the implementation of the act of communication: the source (the speaker); message (text) transmitted through the auditory canal; recipient (listener). At the same time, the act of communication is performed in a certain situation - the sounding text is always addressed to a

specific listener. It is necessary to establish who is speaking and to whom he is addressing. The listener not only perceives the text, but interacts with it.

Texts are essentially meaningless, they acquire it as a result of the interaction of the text with the activity of the listener in understanding this text, so there are situations when we understand much more than was actually said in a given message. The text emits cues that prompt the listener to search their memory for this information, which is then applied again in the text. The text continues to emit signals that encourage the listener to recombine, to add new knowledge to the existing ones. The changed balance of knowledge (information) is a prerequisite for further understanding of the text.

Information goes both in the direction from the text to the listener and from the listener to the text. Therefore, despite the fact that we refer to listening as a receptive type of speech activity, the listener is active, so listening is a perceptual mental-mnemic activity. Perceptual - because there is a direct active reflection of external and internal objects by the cognitive sphere of a person. Cognitive - because its implementation is associated with basic mental operations: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, and comparison, mnemonic (from the Greek mnemonic on - the art of memorization). There are actions of recognition, identification as a result of comparison with the standard stored in memory.

Difficulties in listening - In the practice of teaching a foreign language, listening remained for a long time, as it were, on the periphery of the educational process, and in the methodology of teaching a foreign language it was a kind of "Cinderella", so it is no coincidence that a large number of problems and failures are associated with listening. Let's look at the difficulties in more detail.

The first group of difficulties is the difficulties related to the conditions of perception. Here, the one-time and short-term presentation of information plays an important role, which requires a quick reaction from the listener when perceiving the sounding text. Equally important is the pace set by the speaker. The pace of speaking depends on the particular language. The average rate of English speech is 250 syllables per minute, German - 220, French - 330. This is because the capacity of letters differs in different languages. So, the average German word consists of 6-13 letters, and the English word consists of 4-5 letters. Therefore, the capacity of German letters is lower than that of English letters.

Difficulties in listening are often associated with the source listening (who is it - a live partner in the process of direct contact, a sounding speech from an audio cassette or a radio text during distant listening). At the same time, the influence is exerted by the timbre, the strength of the voice, the individual characteristics of

speech, the existing deviations from the idiomatic normative pronunciation, the gender of the speaker (male or female voice), as well as age. It is known that the understanding of children voices require certain skills.

Many methodologists note that in real communication it is impossible to adjust the duration, volume and clarity of the sound of the text, so the listener gets tired quickly, his attention is scattered, which, in turn, leads to a loss of interest, kills the motivation for further work with the audio text. [1]

The next group of difficulties is related to the perception of the language form and the content of the audio text. It is obvious that the language difficulties of the text distract the listeners from the content and the process of understanding is disturbed. A significant role is played by the length of the sentences perceived by the listener, the presence of unfamiliar lexical, grammatical language material, the presence of homonyms in the information (words belonging to the same part of speech and sounding the same, but different in meaning), for example, der Ball - ball, der Ball - a ball as a dance evening; homophones (words that sound the same but have different spellings): week - days of week, weak - not strong.

There are also so-called false friends of the translator, internationalisms that have a different meaning in a foreign language, words that are used in a figurative sense, polysemantic words, for example, letter - a letter of alphabet, a letter to someone, a paragraph of passage, a person who rents, erudition, etc.

Difficulties related to the content of the audio text are related to understanding the facts (numbers, dates, proper names, geographical names, etc.), the logic of presentation due to the large amount of factual information, as well as the general idea of the text, which often happens if the main idea expressed implicitly, and the text is linguistically complex.

The third group of difficulties is related to the form of presentation of the audio text. The German didact B. Dahlgau, having studied various forms of presenting audio texts (audio text with illustration, listening based on printed text and without support when presenting audio text, single and multiple presentation of the text), believes that listening comprehension of the text depends on factors such as complexity text (the more complex the text, the more support is required to remove difficulties), the language experience of students (the more competent and experienced students are, the faster they are able to give up support in the form of printed text and other illustrations, the faster you can move on to listening to texts without pauses), educational goals and objectives (if the task is to prepare students for a real situation and form a truly auditory competence, one should abandon the printed basis).

In a real communication situation, non-verbal information helps students understand audio texts, for example, facial expressions, gestures; illustrations and photographs can also help in a learning situation. However, from the very beginning of training, the teacher must remember that he is preparing students for a real communication situation, therefore, supports should be reduced, for example, to understand the text without re-listening. [2]

There are difficulties associated with the perception of a certain type of speech activity and type of utterance. It is obvious that it is easier to perceive monologue texts than dialogic ones, and among monologues it is easier to perceive plot texts than descriptive ones.

A special group is the difficulties associated with the socio-cultural part of teaching foreign languages. Ignorance of socio-cultural characteristics can lead to a misunderstanding of the partner's speech behavior, as well as disrupt the understanding of information perceived by ear.

Listening mechanisms and their impact on learning success - Listening as any process is based on certain psycho-physiological mechanisms: perception, recognition and understanding. Perception mechanisms include the mechanism of internal pronunciation, operational and long-term memory, identification (comparison), anticipation (probabilistic forecasting).

The success of listening is associated with the mechanisms of the so-called auditory memory and depends on the size of the "operational unit of perception", i.e., the ability to retain segments of speech in memory. It is on the ability to retain the perceived segments of speech in memory that the process of understanding the audio text, the possibility of its subsequent interpretation, depends. Thanks to auditory operative memory, the student keeps words and phrases in his head, getting the time he needs to comprehend the information he has heard.

However, auditory reception of information is impossible without the participation of internal pronunciation. The effect of understanding depends on the success of the "internal imitation" of audible speech. Thanks to the mechanism of internal pronunciation, sound images turn into articulator ones, there is an "internal imitation" of the perceived audio fragment. If we imitate correctly, then we perceive correctly. [3]

When perceiving speech, there is a constant identification of incoming signals and patterns that are stored in our memory. At the same time, the process of identification is associated with the past experience of a person, as well as with his sensory-emotional sphere. It is obvious that the better long-term memory is developed, the more effective identification occurs.

Researchers have found that even before the start of perception, as soon as the set to listen appears, the articulator organs already show minimal activity. Due to this, certain patterns are aroused in the listener's cognition. Such presetting is the basis for the operation of the anticipation or prediction mechanism, which makes it possible to predict the end of a word or phrase from the beginning. There is linguistic and semantic forecasting.

Linguistic prediction is facilitated by the skill of word compatibility. Knowing the rules for the compatibility of lexical units, students with a greater and lesser degree of probability can predict the content of incoming information, since the word compatibility in the language is limited.

Semantic prediction is provided by the context, the situation of communication, the personal experience of the listener, his knowledge. The success of semantic forecasting largely depends on the listener's expectations. The richer our knowledge of the world, a particular topic or situation, the richer our vocabulary, the greater our ability to predict content and use context clues.

But recognition does not yet understand. The basis of understanding is the mechanism of comprehension, which already functions at the level of actual awareness based on the analytical and synthetic activity of the brain. The comprehension mechanism compresses phrases and individual fragments of text by omitting details and, leaving only semantic milestones in memory, releases it to receive a new piece of information.

The main characteristics of understanding are completeness, precision, depth. The depth of penetration into the meaning of the perceived information indicates the level of understanding. As a rule, two main levels of understanding are distinguished: the meanings of language units, the level of facts and meaning (critical). But there is no single concept in this regard. So, A. R. Luria and other researchers distinguish the following levels of text understanding:

- ✓ fragmentary (individual LU);
- ✓ global (message topics);
- ✓ detailed (of facts);
- ✓ critical (subtext);

Levels of understanding allow you to judge the levels of learning students and specify learning objectives. So, the value of the operational unit of perception depends on internal imitation (correctly imitate → recognize correctly) as a result → identification (continuous comparison of perceived speech with samples of long-term memory), i.e. the better long-term memory, the better identification.

The success of listening depends on the preliminary mood for the audited text. In fact, this is the basis of the method of anticipation, a kind of anticipatory reflection of reality. From recognition, the listener moves to comprehension.

Listening structure - Listening, like any kind of speech activity, has its own peculiar horizontal structure. I.A. Zimnyaya distinguishes three phases in listening: motivational-incentive, analytical-synthetic and performing. [4]

A. A. Leontiev speaks about the need to separate the phase control. The motivational-driven phase is set in motion by the communicative task. Students need to be told before listening what they will listen to and what they specifically need to hear. The motive is created, as a rule, by an interesting exposition, a conversation about the author, the theme of the work. In natural communication, the source of the motive for perception and understanding is the topic of communication and the interlocutor himself (his manner of communication, the ability to attract the attention of the listener, etc.). [5]

The analytical-synthetic phase is the main part of listening. It is here that the perception and processing of information coming through the auditory canal takes place. With the help of the mechanisms described above (auditory memory, prediction, identification, etc.), a conclusion occurs - the result of understanding. All these processes, including the result of auditing itself, are of a hidden nature, i.e., the executive phase in auditing merges with the analytic-synthetic one.

The teacher as decision maker is an area for exploration which includes a vast, and yet poorly understood, dimension of language teaching. Many scholars suggest that teaching is decision making. This means that teachers must make sound decisions in their interactions with students. The number of decisions teachers have to make daily is astonishing. An American educator Murray estimates the number at 1,500. Skilled teachers not only make numerous decisions but also make them well. The effective teacher structures the classroom so that it runs smoothly and efficiently. [6]

In real communication, the result of listening, i.e. understanding remains, as a rule, hidden. In a learning situation, understanding must be made observable in order to teach this type of speech activity. That is why understanding is brought to the external plane, which is carried out at the control phase. With the help of a verbal or non-verbal reaction on the part of the students, the teacher must seek feedback: they understood or did not understand, they succeeded or failed to solve the communicative task. According to scientists, the perception of information by ear occupies a fairly large place in the lesson: from 40 to 60%.

USED LITERATURES:

- 1) Listening training: textbook. allowance / ed. E. I. Passova, E. S. Kuznetsova. - Voronezh: NOU "Interlingua", 2002. - (Ser. Methods of teaching foreign languages; No. 12). - 40 s.
- 2) Passov E.I. Foreign language lesson in secondary school / E.I. Passov. - M.: Education, 1988. - 223 p.
- 3) Dahlhaus B. Fernstudieneinheit 5. Fertigkeit Hören / Barbara Dahlhaus. – Berlin : Langenscheidt, 2007. – 193 S.
- 4) Zimnyaya I. A. Psychology of teaching a non-native language: (on the material of Russian as a foreign language). M., 1989.
- 5) Zhinkin N. I. Speech as a conductor of information. M., 1982.
- 6) Ravshanova Nasiba Karamatovna Teaching Foreign Language Speaking” Article Doi:- <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/> Volume02Issue11-13 Volume 02 Issue11 November 2022.